

International Conference on **ICGB 2017** Green Banking Perceptions and Challenges

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(A Constituent College of Mangalore University)
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC

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Excel
INDIA PUBLISHERS

EXCEL INDIA PUBLISHERS
NEW DELHI

First Impression: February, 2017

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International Conference on Green Banking: Perceptions and Challenges

ISBN: 978-93-86256-39-3

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Published by

EXCEL INDIA PUBLISHERS

91 A, Ground Floor
Pratik Market, Munirka, New Delhi-110067
Tel: +91-11-2671 1755/ 2755/ 3755/ 5755
Fax: +91-11-2671 6755

E-mail: publishing@groupexcelindia.com

Web: www.groupexcelindia.com

Typeset by

Excel Publishing Services, New Delhi-110067

E-mail: prepress@groupexcelindia.com

Printed by

Excel Printing Universe, New Delhi-110067

E-mail: printing@groupexcelindia.com

Opportunities and Challenges of Green Banking

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Abstract—Sustainable development can be achieved by allowing market towards efficiency and economic development. Financial institution such as banking sector is one of the major economic agent which influence overall industrial growth of a country. Green banking is a modern and new concept of banking where all financial activities remains same but extra focus is given on sustainability and environmental protection through paperless banking by this save natural resources in the nature. Now a day people are so connected to computer, computer literacy helps easy to start green banking practices Most of the customers are using ATM cards. So, this is the best and to start all the initiatives for green banking practices. As per green banking is concerned Indian banks and financial institutions are running behind time. Most of Indian banks or financial institutions have not yet adopted using green banking products so, it is time now that India takes some major steps to use environmental sensitive parameter apart from financial to fund projects.

Keywords: Green Banking, Sustainable Development, Swipe Machine, Opportunities, Challenges

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development can be achieved by allowing market towards efficiency and economic development. Financial institution such as banking sector is one of the major economic agent which influence overall industrial growth of a country. In maintain sustainability bank plays a important role. Sustainable development leads to shift focus from traditional approach like profit making to environmental protection with the purpose of fulfilling the dual role the first role is work towards achieving ethical and social responsible banking and second role is corporate social responsibility. In recent days every global leader is telling about global warming and carbon footprint which is affecting the day to day life. It is the responsibility of every individual to contribute reducing global temperature to save mankind. Keeping in the mind we would like to introduce Green Banking system which can contribute global warming and the nature. Green banking gives solution for paper less business transaction in today market. Our Prime Minister of India has an vision of digital India in 21st century, which can be adopted in banking system by using Green Banking products. Banks now realized about present paper explore and environmental effects, thus shifted towards green banking products and procedure are SBI and ICICI.

MEANING OF GREEN BANKING

Green banking is one of the activities of bank in which bank play vital role between economic growth and environmental protection under this bank takes some action to reduce carbon emissions, in this should finance green technology and pollution reducing projects. Green banking is nothing but a normal bank in which bank takes some initiatives to encourage environmental friendly investment, which includes social and environmental factors with an aim to protect environment and natural resources by reducing paper work in his transaction by this save trees and reduce carbon footprint in environment.

Green banking is a modern and new concept of banking where all financial activities remains same but extra focus is given on sustainability and environmental protection through paperless banking by this save natural resources in the nature.

OBJECTIVES OF GREEN BANKING

- Educating traditional approach of paperless banking in day to day transaction.
- Adopting advanced technology in banking system.
- Educating usage of green banking products.
- Creating awareness about green banking among people in the society.

PRODUCT OR METHODS OF GREEN BANKING

GREEN LOANS

Banks are providing loans to assist small scale industries, business and individuals in commencing and expanding eco-friendly products and services. Green loans are primarily granted for recycling, waste management activities, composting to build a community gardens, solar panels and window and green landscaping.

ATM (AUTOMATED TELLER MACHINE)

ATM is also known as cash machine. ATM enables the customer or financial institutions to perform financial transactions just like cash withdrawal and cash deposits through ATM machine without need for human intervention. It is a process of inserting ATM cards or smart cards with a check that contains unique card number. It also contain security information such as expiry date CVV (card verification value) and PIN (personal identification number).

ONLINE BANKING

It is also known as internet banking or E-banking. It helps customer and other financial institution to do a financial transaction through websites. In other words it is a system allowing individuals to perform banking activities at home via internet. Online banking helps to perform all routine transactions such as account transfer, balance enquiries, bill payment, online loans and credit card application.

MOBILE BANKING

It is a service provided by banks and financial institutions it allows its customer to conduct financial transaction through mobile phone or tablet. Through mobile banking we can perform account balance checking, electronic bill payment, fund transfers between customers or other account so, mobile applications also enable copies of statements to be downloaded or printed at customer premises. It reduces cost of handling transaction, customer visiting to a bank and helps in paperless banking.

GREEN CREDIT CARDS

Green credit cards are so unique cards which are designed to fight climate change and sustain the planet. It reduces our personal carbon foot print. It mainly funds for rainforest preservation and reforestation. Most of the banks will donate funds to non-profit organization which mainly concern with environment by using green credit cards.

SWIPE MACHINE

Banks are providing POS machine facilities this leads to paperless as well as cashless transaction. In retail business like shopping malls, hotels, petrol banks and many other business outlets. Our Indian Prime minister will know adopting this technology he give more importance to cashless transaction.

OPPORTUNITIES

- Now a day people are so connected to computer, computer literacy helps easy to start green banking practices
- Most of the customers are using ATM cards. So, this is the best and to start all the initiatives for green banking practices
- Due to mobile resolution mobile banking opportunities are increasing day by day. So, we can spread the green banking practices through mobile banking
- Internet banking or the E-banking also helps to spread the green banking practices
- Creation of financial products and services that support the commercial development with environmental benefit
- Stakeholders should be aware about environmental issues and benefits of green banking
- Adoption of green banking technologies should not be considered as financial burden by banks. It should be considered as a new opportunities for higher profit
- Bank should encourage, motivate the work force to follow green banking practices and also encourage its customers and supplier to adopt and follow the green practices

OTHER OPPORTUNITIES

SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

When a company makes products from the parts purchased from suppliers and those products are sold to customer is called supply chain management.

- We can adopt various techniques and plans to minimize inventory wastage like use of scrape materials, improving quality, inventory control, lean manufacturing, recycling and better warehousing management.
- Carbon foot print design

Carbon foot print define as the total amount of green house gases produce to directly and indirectly human activities which is express in equalent tons of carbon dioxide by adoption of a good footprint design we can help environment through purchasing wind power and adoption of reforestation and forest preservation and reduce electrical consumption.

CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT

It refers to a practice, strategies and technologies used by companies to manage and analyses the customer interaction. We can help environment sustainability by adoption of electronic means to maintain contact and corresponding with customer.

ENTERPRISE RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

There are lot of oppotunities in enterprise resource management by adoption of promoting paperless transaction.

Eg: Online billing, online payment, online money transfer, maintenance of various data through internet server.

BENEFITS OF GOING GREEN

REDUCE TRANSACTION COST OF BANK

Green bank avails paper work through following of electronic media for various transaction, bank functioning and customer management.

Eg: by providing E-statements to customers, opening account through online, internal transfers through online etc.

Will needs paperless banking which reduce transaction cost and also save trees.

MANAGE COMPETITION

It helps banks to manage market competitions through innovation in their products and services.

EASY LOAN RECOVERY

It helps banks to manage competition through innovation in their products and services available to the customers.

BETTER RISK MANAGEMENT

It helps bank to manage various risk. Better risk management helps in building good image of banks and by thus reducing the reputational risk.

Green banking helps in easy recovery of loan which reduces the credit risk of the bank.

REDUCTION OF TRANSACTION COST OF CUSTOMER

The transaction cost can be reduced through green banking products like ATM, mobile banking and online banking whereas customer visiting the bank branch and performing will be costly.

CHALLENGES OF GREEN BANKING

DIVERSIFICATION PROBLEM

Green banking restrict their business for qualify screening process done by green banks with limited number of customer. They will be having smaller base to support. Most of the customers do not have computer literacy so, it is very difficult to diversify from branch banking to internet banking or mobile banking.

START UP FACE OR NEW FACE

Many banks are adopting green banking as a very initial stage or in startup face generally it take 3-4 years for bank to start generating revenue. Thus, it does not help bank during recession.

HIGH OPERATING COST

Green banks required highly qualified, experienced staff to provide services to customer, experienced loan officers also required for dealing with green business and customers which needs to high operating cost.

REPUTATIONAL RISK

In case of internet crimes and cyber hacking customers may face lot of issues which may damage reputation of the bank it leads to breach of trust of customer.

CREDIT RISK

Credit risk may arise by lending credit to those customers whose business is affected by cost of pollution environmental regulation etc. So, there is a higher probability of customer default. It leads to reduction capital investment loss of market shares and affect third party claims.

OPERATING PROBLEM

All people in the society are not fully aware about green banking, people are not fully educated about green bank products like Net banking, Mobile banking Credit & Debit card etc, due to illiteracy many people are not know how to use green banking products and some bank staffs are also not aware about it therefore, it is difficult for bank to take some initiatives under green banking process. Therefore, the initiatives taken by the banks will not get successful every time

SUGGESTION

- Educate customer about green banking
- Encourage customer to use green banking products like net banking, mobile banking, ATM cards etc.
- Construct website and educate people green banking education through E-learning program spread green banking related information as a part of annual report
- Training bank staff and employees about green banking
- Banks may introduce green funds for its customers which helps in investing environmental friendly products
- The banks may give concession or discount in loan or interest for those who actively participate in environmental friendly activities.

CONCLUSION

Green banking refers to initiatives taken by banks to encourage environmental friendly investment. The present study finds that the young generation is interested towards green banking products. Therefore there is a more of need to create awareness about green banking products adoption among middle and senior age group. Green banking affects the banks and financial institution to recover their return from investment so, the bank should play an important role to take environmental and ecological aspect as a part of their lending principle. This will force industries to use appropriate technology and management system under environmental system. As per green banking is concerned Indian banks and financial institutions are running behind time. Most of Indian banks or financial institutions have not yet adopted using green banking products so, it is time now that India takes some major steps to use environmental sensitive parameter apart from financial to fund projects.

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